

BUILDING STRONG DEMOCRATIC INSTITUTIONS: A PANACEA TO GOOD GOVERNANCE AND POLICY IMPLEMENTATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Democratic rule in Nigeria since 29th May 1999 has been stable and devoid of military intervention. The stability is predicated on the resolution of the people of Nigeria to institutionalized development and replicate standard global governance. The greatest challenge hindering the growth of democratic values is the issue of political corruption. Corruption has challenged the challenges of democratic governance. Three democratic institutions were looked into in this study. These are, Independent Electoral Commission (INEC), Independent and other Related Crimes Commission (ICPC) and the Economic Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), in view of their peculiar nature and the role they play in the economy of Nigeria. The study was conducted with the aid of materials from secondary sources. The paper supports institutionalization of the legislature and the need to build and strengthen the nation's democratic institutions and further encourage the implementation of governmental policies for the sustainability of peace and equity. Usually, frequent changes in the political and social context could alter the configuration of support for policy formulations mid implementation. Successful policy implementation has become synonymous with growth and development of an economy. The current vision 20:2020 of President Goodluck Jonathan keyed into the developmental strife of the present administration if properly harnessed. The paper therefore submits that good governance and democratic principles could be sustained, if these democratic institutions are strengthened in line with the policies establishing them.

Introduction

From independence in 1960 to the present, Nigerian governments, whether civilian or military, have not differed substantially on their economic policy. Each supported the concept of a mixed economy—a public sector controlled by the state and a private sector or free enterprise—and state intervention in such social sectors as education and health. This was in accord with the system of economy inherited at independence from Britain.

The consolidation of the foundation for democracy set clear rules and strict control over the activities of politicians. It was therefore expected that political parties, civil society groups and other critical stakeholders in Nigerian electoral process needed to brazen up to the challenges [Adetula, 2008:25]. In order to underscore the importance that the present administration of President Goodluck Jonathan attaches to true democracy, good governance and accountability, the President has time without number promised not to interfere with the democratic institutions' activities in the country, especially in the areas of dealing with corrupt government officials and electoral matters of the Independent Electoral Commission. The April 2011, elections of the most populous country in Africa

and a growing player on the global scene (Nigeria), went through a series of electoral processes. Suffice the writer to say that, in the 21st century, capable, reliable, and transparent institutions are the key to success -- strong parliaments; honest police forces; independent judges; an independent press; a vibrant private sector; a civil society. Those are the things that give life to democracy, because that is what matters in people's everyday lives. We do not need strongmen we need strong institutions. In fact, Nigerian's policy goal is to nurture the development of stable and democratic institutions that are committed to the rule of law, human rights, transparent governance, and the welfare of its citizens. This paper believes that the long-term strategy of supporting, strengthening and sustaining democratic institutions is already paying off. As a result, priority must be given to funding for democracy programs which reinforces good governance and the rule of law, and promote participation of women and civil society. However, some African governments lack the will to conduct free and fair elections in which they might lose political and economic power. Instead, they rig the system by monopolizing the media, harassing opposition figures, and otherwise closing political space. On a continent where most political and economic power still resides in the State, elections are too often viewed as a zero sum game in which all spoils go to the winner.

Democracy cannot be sustained if the electoral system remains an object of manipulations by politicians [Zamako, 2009:7]. This paper is also of the view that electoral autocracy has numerous negative consequences, as captured in the data in international reports and studies compiled by Freedom House, the Mo Ibrahim Index, Transparency International, and the World Bank, among others. Most reveal a variety of problems including corruption, a lack of accountability, crony capitalism, and nepotism. These elements feed a rent-seeking class of well-connected elites who maintain a stranglehold on local economies. This behavior crowds out legitimate local entrepreneurs and fuels large disparities in income and opportunity. This can breed anger, resentment and even violence, as we have seen in the countries impacted by the Arab Spring.

Nigeria Vision 20:2020 is a call for all Nigerians, regardless of ethnicity, economic status, or religion to unite and stand behind a common cause of placing the country firmly on a path of sustainable growth, and taking it to its rightful place in the comity of nations. The vision is underpinned by the need to effectively and efficiently mobilize the nation's resources to serve and improve the lives of its citizens, and to respond appropriately to the growing challenges of an increasingly smaller, mutually dependent, and interconnected world [NV20:2020:4]. The political and economic success of Nigeria depends a great deal on the effectiveness, sustainability, and reliability of its democratic institutions. That means a focus on process and progress, not personalities. Leaders must recognize that building long-term ties with their people culminates into credibility, strong and independent institutions which are the key to

both a deeper relationship with the international community and to their long-term success, these forms the base of a good democracy.

A good democracy is thus first and foremost a broadly legitimated regime that completely satisfies citizens (*quality in terms of result*). When institutions have the full backing of civil society, they can pursue the values of the democratic regime. If, in contrast, the institutions must postpone their objectives and expend energy and resources on consolidating and maintaining their legitimacy, crossing over even the minimum threshold for democracy becomes a remarkable feat. Secondly, good democracy is one in which the citizens, associations, and communities of which it is composed enjoy at least a moderate level of liberty and equality (*quality in terms of content*). Thirdly, in a good democracy it is the citizens themselves who have the power to check and evaluate whether the government pursues the objectives of liberty and equality according to the rule of law. They monitor the efficiency of the application of the laws in force, the efficacy of the decisions made by government, and the political responsibility and accountability of elected officials in relation to the demands expressed by civil society (*quality in terms of procedure*) [Leonard, 2002:4].

Need for Sustainable and Democratic Institutions in Nigeria

Nigeria generally shows a pronounced commitment to democracy. If democracy is "government by the people," then a reliable means is needed to know what "the people" want. Elections perform this function, but only if freely and fairly conducted and then only once every several years. This paper is expected to draw the attention of those in authority or relevant bodies to take into consideration the importance of building a viable and sustainable institution that would address the inadequacies and the non-functionality of the Nigerian state.

This paper is also of the view that continued support efforts of the International Community especially the United States of America to strengthen democratic institutions and participation will lead to good governance, strengthening parliaments, and increasing the efficiency of the nation's judicial systems, and continue to provide assistance to encourage civic participation, so that young people get involved, and to fund concrete solutions to corruption such as forensic accounting to advance transparency and accountability.

The paper further hark on the need to have an effective economic development program that could help build democratic institutions, as it is said "an empowered citizenry is the foundation of every strong democracy". Hence policy is built on anticipating that change that is inevitable and can best be channeled through constructive action rather than destructive reaction, is geared towards the highlight of importance of building strong democratic institutions, good governance, accountability and the role

of civil society. In view of these therefore, the paper seeks to evaluate the three democratic institutions i.e. EFCC, ICPC and INEC; find out the reasons behind the ineffectiveness of state structures; find out the challenges of policy implementation in Nigeria in relation with good governance; and ascertain the relationship between policy implementation and target (economic) values.

Advancing Liberal Democracy for the Sustenance of Democratic Institutions

Liberal democracy is a form of government that operates under the principles of liberalism. It is characterized by fair, free, and competitive elections between multiple distinct political parties, the rule of law in everyday life as part of an open society, a separation of powers into different branches of government, and the protection of human rights and civil liberties for all persons. To define the system in practice liberal democracies often draw upon a constitution, either formally written or uncodified, to delineate the powers of government and enshrine the social contract. After a period of sustained expansion throughout the 20th century, liberal democracy became the predominant political system in the world. According to Saidai the main slogan of liberalism right from inception, has been liberty i.e. freedom of the individual to develop all of his potentialities as a human being [wikipedia].

Empiricists have argued that the theory of liberal democracy is one thing, its practice quite another. Examples of this are Robert Putnam at Harvard and Bent Flyvbjerg at Oxford [Putnam et al 1993] [Flyvbjerg, 1998]. Both argue that in liberal democracies "the rules are not the game," i.e. the rules of democracy, as written down in democratic constitutions, do not ensure democracy and that "constitution writing" is not the most effective way to improve liberal democracies. Putnam found that the existence and cultivation of "social capital" are more important to making liberal democracy work in practice than the constitutions and formal institutions of democracy. Flyvbjerg found that organizations and citizens in a liberal democracy are experts at judging how far a democratic constitution and institution can be bent and used in nondemocratic ways for group and personal advantage. Democratic rationality is confronted by opportunistic political power at every turn, and typically "power has a rationality that rationality does not know," in the words of Flyvbjerg (2001: 154), who argues that effective checks and balances on power are what matters to make liberal democracy work in practice.

Liberal democracies usually have universal suffrage, granting all adult citizens the right to vote regardless of race, gender or property ownership. Historically, however, some countries regarded as liberal democracies have had a more limited franchise, and some do not have secret ballots. There may also be qualifications such as voters being required to register before being allowed to vote like in the case of Nigeria. The decisions made through elections are made not by all of the citizens, but rather by

those who choose to participate by voting.

The liberal democratic constitution defines the democratic character of the state. The purpose of a constitution is often seen as a limit on the authority of the government. Liberal democracy emphasizes the separation of powers, an independent judiciary, and a system of checks and balances between branches of government. Liberal democracies are likely to emphasize the importance of the state that follows the principle of the rule of law. Governmental authority is legitimately exercised only in accordance with written, publicly disclosed laws adopted and enforced in accordance with established procedure. Many democracies use federalism-also known as vertical separation of powers, in order to prevent abuse and increase public input by dividing governing powers between municipal, provincial and national governments [wikipedia.org].

For countries without a strong tradition of democratic majority rule, the introduction of free elections alone has rarely been sufficient to achieve a transition from dictatorship to democracy; a wider shift in the political culture and gradual formation of the institutions of democratic government are needed. There are various examples, for instance in Latin America, of countries that were able to sustain democracy only temporarily or in a limited fashion until wider cultural changes established the conditions under which democracy could flourish. One of the key aspects of democratic culture is the concept of a "loyal opposition". This is an especially difficult cultural shift to achieve in nations where transitions of power have historically taken place through violence. The term means, in essence, that all sides in a democracy share a common commitment to its basic values. Political competitors may disagree, but they must tolerate one another and knowledge the legitimate and important roles that each play. The ground rules of the society must encourage tolerance and civility in public debate. In such a society, the losers accept the judgment of the voters when the election is over, and allow for the peaceful transfer of power. The losers are safe in the knowledge that they will neither lose their lives nor their liberty, and will continue to participate in public life. They are loyal not to the specific policies of the government, but to the fundamental legitimacy of the state and to the democratic process itself.

Conceptual Clarification

- ❖ Institutionalization was defined in terms of the processes by which such patterns achieve normative and cognitive fixity, and should not be taken for granted [Meyer. et.a!., 1987].
- ❖ The Independent Corrupt Practices & Other Related Commission (ICPC) is the apex body saddled by the law with the responsibility to fight corruption and other related offences in Nigeria. It 'was set up and empowered by the Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act 2000, to employ all available legal means to rid Nigeria of all forms of corruption and thus promote transparency, probity, accountability

and integrity in the public and private life of all Nigerians.

- ❖ The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) is the main agent of democracy in Nigeria. INEC a permanent body created by the constitution to organize Federal and state elections in Nigeria was to amongst others, educate Nigerian citizens about democracy and the election process; provide for voter registration; compile a credible voters' register; demarcate constituency boundaries; organize and conduct credible elections; monitor the conduct of political parties; audit the finances of political parties, and promote an enduring democratic culture in Nigeria.
- ❖ While the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) is a Nigerian law enforcement agency that investigates financial crimes such as advance fee fraud (419 fraud) and money laundering. The EFCC was established in 2003, partially in response to pressure from the Financial Action Task Force on Money Laundering (FA TF), which named Nigeria as one of 23 countries non-cooperative in the international community's efforts to fight money laundering [The Establishment Act, 2007].
- ❖ Policies are typically described as principles or rules to guide decisions and achieve rational outcome(is). The term is not normally used to denote what is actually done; this is normally referred to as either procedure or protocol [Anderson, 2005:1]. It also has to do with statements issued by the Government on activities to be carried out to address certain issues that affect the citizenry. Usually too, these statements are geared towards the development of the society if properly implemented. Policies are supposed to address the social needs of the people.
- ❖ The implementation of policies has been advanced by so many authors in explaining the ingredients of good governance and stable democracy. Policy implementation is the stage of policy-making between the establishment of a policy and the consequences of the policy for the people whom it affects. For the effectiveness of these therefore the paper adopts good governmental policy implementation.

Strengthening Democratic institutions and Sustaining Democratic Principles in Nigeria

Jepperson (1991) posited that early accounts identified institutional effects as concerned principally with social stability, drawing attention to reproductive processes that function as stable patterns for sequence of activities that were routinely enacted [1991: 143-163], while thinkers have also long recognized that institutions interact with one another in ways that can be studied and understood. It was in relation to this that Zamako said that forces are not only economic and political, but are also social and cultural [2009: 171]. Thus, informed Karl Marx contribution, were he asserted that people's ideas are conditioned by their economic environment [Leon,1979:75-167]. Adam Smith a physiocrat advocated for economic freedom, especially freedom from governmental regulations in the economic

affairs. The focus on this paper is the building of strong democratic institutions that culminates into good and effective governance, where corrupt practices are addressed by relevant agencies and the right to vote and be voted is sustained. As Zamako rightly said the whole concept of representation in democracy is an attempt to ensure the involvement of everybody in government and its process or at least, to ensure that all people have the feeling and opportunity of being' part of government [2009: 17]. Surely nobody would say that democracy is the best system imaginable. Assuming a utopian system impossible, quite a few would suppose that it is the best possible system in practice. However, there is hardly a consensus on what constitutes democracy; it lists representative and liberal, Islamic and Christian, constitutional, grassroots, and even totalitarian democracies among its congregation. So newer, better kinds of democracy are certainly imaginable, if not necessarily practicable. Edmund Burke argued that a good government is one that keeps its peace [Leon,1979:74]. Good democratic governance therefore requires that the government is held accountable; that the citizens are consulted and their interests taken into account; and that policies are implemented swiftly, correctly, and consistently.

Kapstein and Converse believed that building and sustaining democratic institutions alone does not guarantee the spread of democratic politics - the consolidation or 'deepening' of democratic norms and principles in every area of governance and society is a more complex and long-term process of change [2008:4]. While some have argued that existing donor approaches to democracy promotion have neglected local concerns, this paper believed that this critique is too sweeping.

The most serious problem with democracy promotion has been a failure to defend core liberal norms. Experts have tended to focus on economic performance as political institutions are crucial for democratic consolidation. If sustained economic growth ultimately depends on the quality of a nation's institutions, the industrial world's aid programs may have the causal chain backward. What is most important however is the extent to which the benefits of economic reform are widely shared. It is important to look beyond economics and consider political institutions. It was in these regard that Rakner, Rocha and Fritz, advised that democracy assistance must emphasize the crucial role of effective checks and balances-informal as well as formal-in building of durable democratic institutions [2007].

Challenges of Democratic Institutions

The global spread of democracy has proven more conflictual than anyone could have imagined when it began. Woodward (1996), opined that "the collapse of communist regimes in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union and of patrimonial dictatorships in Africa, opened the way to the establishment of fledgling democracies in some countries." But in many others, it merely introduced more decentralized forms of oppression and armed conflict. Moreover, misconceived efforts by Western powers to force the pace of economic and political

liberation have frequently been blamed (as in Rwanda) for the escalation of political violence.

Yet as Claude Ake has argued, the problems may not be with democracy as such, but with how it has been introduced, including the failure to anticipate the spoiling tactics of former beneficiaries of non-democratic governance [1996:8]. "Democratization" he argues, may be used to have some conflict potential, since it entails redistribution of power which is invariably resisted by those in power, ... (But) why should the burden of conflict lie on those who are engaged in emancipatory struggles for participation and a just order? Why should it not rather lie on those who aggressively, and often violently, deny others their entitlements? This could be the reason why Jefferson asserted that all people were created equal, that "the Laws of nature and Nature's God" had given every person a set of rights that could not be legally alienated, and that among those rights were "Life, Liberty and the pursuit of Happiness" [Leon,1979:80].

In addition, several decades of failed developmental efforts in Nigeria, the persistent deterioration in the quality of life of the average Nigerian, the worsening conditions of public utilities and the enduring poor economic performance have combined to stimulate scholars to ask questions which are of practical administrative interest and of great concern. Some critics have also observed that the foundation of the problems lies in the arena of plan lessness and problem identification and the embedment of personal interest in policy and decision making in the country. Hence in any given economy, the various components should reflect the well-being of others. As depression in one sector invariably transfer itself to others to some extent [Walter, 1972: 115].

Criminalizing corruption is not enough! The law must ensure transparency. Declaration of asset publicly should be the norm and not the exception. The system must be programmed in a way that it is difficult for public officers to hide anything regarding their finances. Family members of public officers should also be made to undergo public scrutiny. This could be the reason why the United States Government urged Nigerian elected and senior public officials to make their assets declaration public. Laolu added that the President of the United States and other elected and senior public officials normally release their income statements on a yearly basis especially during the time they file their yearly taxes [2012:3]. The law should ensure seamless collaboration amongst agencies and not contradictory roles, hence it need to be clear on who does what, defines nature of cooperation and limit unnecessary interference by coordinate agencies. Strengthening institutions as argued above require legislation. This will call for a review of the existing legal framework especially as it regards to anti-graft institutions, as suggested by the Nigerian Bar Association President - Olisa Agbakoba.

Furthermore, some perceive challenges democratic institutions faced in their efforts to assist the processes of democracy is how to engage with hybrid regimes, i.e. donors need to focus on strengthening accountability and oversight mechanisms and on supporting institutions that can counter-balance the power of the executive; harmonization and alignment in democratization assistance urgently needs to

be addressed, particularly in the context of hybrid regimes, where donor fragmentation and lack of country ownership further undermine already weak institutions.

Recent analysts argued that few African political systems have so far developed into institutionalized, consolidated democracies - where democratic institutions and rules have become 'the only game in town [Linz, et.al.,1996]. Admittedly attempts to classify the range of Africa regimes according to their levels of democratic development are fraught with problems of data, interpretation and short time series [Lindberg,2006]. If people cannot benefit from democracy tangibly, it is because the system still lacks sound, selfless and moral political leadership that has the fear of God at heart, to deal righteously [Zamako, 2009:39]. To this end, a comprehensive review of ethnic balancing measures and diversity management related laws (e.g. federal character) should be undertaken with a view to ensuring greater promotion of merit while retaining the substance of their original intent [Osaghae,1989:443]. Robert Dahl argues that, "the fundamental democratic principles" is when it comes to binding collective decisions, each person in a political community is entitled to have his/her interests be given equal consideration (not necessarily that all people are equally satisfied by the collective decision) [Dahl, 1989:14].

Economic Viability in Strengthening Democratic Institution

Leon (1979) in quoting Edmund Burke, said that the institutions of any society are the products of the accumulated wisdom of centuries. He said that no single generation had the ability to produce abrupt changes that will improve a system [Leon, 1979:74]. Therefore, institution building is a long process that yields long-term benefits.

Ikelegbe (2006: 127) rightly argued that, economic development is important in determining levels of government spending, services and other policy output. He added that the levels of certain functions of governmental activities and services are to a large extent a function of socio-economic resources. Well-designed, appropriate institutions serve as the foundations to economic growth and good democratic governance. Schweitzer (1962:76) postulated that the institutions of successful economies and democracies both rest on clear, transparent rules that foster stability, opportunity and freedom. It is simply an illusion to talk of development in any society whose members lack moral maturity and social responsibility, for moral laxity and irresponsibility on the part of the members of any society is an obstacle, the greatest obstacle to the development of that society. It was to give credence to this assertion that Jide Ojo (2008: 108), added that there should be a law permitting the auditing of campaign donations to candidates and added that any excess money not expended on the campaign should either be forfeited to government or donated in aid of some public cause.

Promoting Good Governance and Enhancing Democratic Institutions

Nigerians clearly have high expectations of democratic governance, and considerable optimism about their future. The presence of democracy is not sufficient enough if its institutional structure does not provide good governance. According to Ole (2001: 19) he asserted that democracy consists not only of central constitutional structures that process the demand of citizens and outputs of central institutions. It also structures the way in which civil society institutions functions (parties and organizations), and the way implementation agencies (executive and judicial) and institutions accomplish the tasks entrusted to them. He added that institutions that are integral parts of democratic consolidation, and the assumption about how individual preference intersect with the consolidation of institutions must be considered when applying the insights of institutional theory to empirical cases of democratic consolidation in the institutions. This is, the role ascribed to institutions and organizations in the process of democratization which depends on how we *ex ante* perceive the interaction between institutions and political actors. While Zamako argued that, universal suffrage, majority rule, rule of law, transparent conduct of regular elections, presence of alternative political parties, exercise of, and respect for fundamental human rights and an impartial judiciary must be in place, for the soul of democracy is that every individual should be able to participate in the process of government without inhibition [2009: 12]. In many countries where democracy has made inroads and elections have been held, the majority of the population has yet to experience tangible improvements in their lives. In these countries, many may question the practicality of democracy or acquire a distorted understanding of what democracy really entails. They may become susceptible to populist or authoritarian appeals that are camouflaged as democracy. The best way to improve the lot of these people is to achieve greater reform and more complete democracy, not to compromise political or economic freedoms. The paramount need is for better governance. While elections create a basis for popular representation, a working, responsive government is the *sine qua non* for improving people's lives. Aristotle was looking at it from this context when he described democracy as the rule by the many or majority, while his underlying principle of democracy was freedom, since only in democracy the citizen can have a share in freedom.

The strengthening of Nigerian's democratic governance will involve tackling our perennial challenge of conducting free and fair elections while instituting a system of government that is transparent and accountable [NV20:2020:16]. The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) being the main agent of democracy in Nigeria and also saddled with the mandate to conduct the federal, state and local government elections has promised to be transparent, uphold integrity, credible, impartial and dedicated to serve the Nigerian state. Omoregie rightly wrote that any government made up of dishonest and

fraudulent people whose main purpose of coming to government is to enrich themselves is not a government, but a gang of thieves and treasury looters [2008:127]. The need to develop our political institutions cannot therefore be overemphasized.

A democratic system of government in Nigeria must have a properly tailored institutional design in order to effectively manage the country's unique ethnic, political and social situation. These institutions provide representation for all groups, encourage cooperation and coalition building across ethnic lines in order to address the main challenges of democracy in divided societies [Ryan,2005]. Such institutions are saddled with the responsibilities of building a unique society towards the enhancement of development in the society. These institutions have their aims and objectives, powers and limitations, etc., spelt out by the laws establishing them. As Burke rightly said, the strength of an institution comes from the fact that it is accepted by the citizens in a society [Leon, 1979:75].

Political freedom and equality, which, according to the theory of liberalism, are expressed in the right to vote, have no meaning except on a basis that excludes inequality of fundamental economic conditions. Therefore, the principle of democracy is essential to the open debate upon which a vibrant political culture is founded and maintained. According to Robert Burns he said that the strongest power is that which can forbid its own mention. Anybody who attempts to suppress political debate should be suspected of trying to defend illegitimate power. Burns observed that five main principles should be adhered for democracy to thrive in any society. These are: i. freedom of speech; ii. open accountable and diverse mass media; iii. popular democracy; iv. economic democracy for the people; and, v. equality before the law [www.sovereignty].

Government should begin to put popular democratic values rather than representative democracy. The people should retain and exercise the policy-making and law-making initiative, rather than being subject to it. For example, the Islamic banking initiative and the cashless society programmes recently introduced by the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2011, and the pronouncement by the government on the removal of oil subsidy from PMS (petrol) in 2012, to mention but a few. In a popular democracy, the government is the servant of the people, not their master. Its job is to listen, respond and deliver to that which is demanded by the people.

Constitutes of Successful Policy Implementation

At the simplest level, "implementation represents the faithful fulfillment of policy intentions by public servants" [Calista, 1994: 117-155]. Newcomers to business and government often assume that a policy, once adopted, will be implemented in accord with the policy makers' intent. An increasingly rich

body of research confirms what old hands know - that is just not the case. Practitioners and scholars have come to understand that policy adoption is simply one milestone in a continuing process of addressing an issue. Researchers have concluded, however, that implementation is a critical part of policy making process. Policy is adopted and adapted and drifts, morphs, and mutates through the implementation process. The extent of drift and mutation depends on a myriad of variables, only some of which can be controlled by policy makers. Calista's assessment of the field of study is that it evolved from one of viewing implementation as simply the process of carrying out policy directives to where implementation "is now integral to the field of policy intervention, including recognizing its influence on policy formulation". Evidence continues to mount demonstrating that, often, policies are not implemented in accord with the policy makers' intent. Indeed, it may be that successful implementation is the exception rather than the rule. Calista in citing Derthick (1990) reports that the most prevalent finding in implementation research is that outcomes are either disappointing or unwitting [ibid]. Others suggest that policy implementation is "the continuation of politics with other means". [Majone and Wildacsky, 1978:103-117].

Therefore, successful implementation is not the same as solving the problem. It is entirely possible that a program could be implemented exactly as intended and that the program is ineffective because the problem transformed during the implementation period or because the program was flawed conceptually. If a local government provides incentives for action by private actors, some will choose to participate and others will not. It is possible that an overwhelming majority act in such a way as to convince even the most jaded skeptic that the policy has been implemented. Suppose, however, that only 10 percent of those targeted by the policy and eligible to participate actually volunteer to participate in the program or implement the policy. Is policy implementation successful? Presumably not, because such a small proportion of the target was reached. Careful diagnosis of the implementation process might focus attention on a specific aspect of the program designed to implement the policy, such as providing greater incentive or engaging in more effective campaigns to make members of the target audience more aware of the program. If each of the organizations in the implementation net does precisely what is called for in an agency's program plan, but, still, the private citizens or organizations targeted for action fail to take the steps that bring about clear intent of the public policy, is implementation successful or has it failed? Ikelegbe asserted that, sometimes the enthusiasm, inspiration, momentum, capacities and quick substantive results which are required in policy implementation may not be obtainable in the existing government agencies, this he said could lead to the establishment of governmental structures, or entirely new structures [2006:206].

The implementation of governmental policies as it relates to addressing corruption can't

therefore be overemphasized. Such policies must seem to work towards ensuring that the progress and protection of citizenry and the development of the nation at large is addressed as policies are principles rules and guidelines formulated by government to reach its long term and desired goals. This is also what the new institutionalism portends as the theory advocated for institutional arrangements which should respond to important distribution of political power across groups and their antecedent interests. This is richly born out in Robert Bates's important arguments concerning government agricultural policies in other parts of Africa and in Jack Knight's efforts to frame the conflictual elements of institutions.

Stability of Democracy in the Promotion of Democratic Institution

The contribution of a neoclassical democratic theorist like Edmund Burke (1729-1797), was to justify a political system that he hoped would become a reality. Burke was a second wave political thinker who believed that an existing institution had value. That is, an existing institution is a product of the wisdom of generations, which has proved its value by surviving and should therefore not be trifled with. The institutions would have disappeared if they were not useful, he said. The advocacy to strengthen and stabilize democratic institution cannot be overemphasized as absolute power comes from the society and the state. Burke wrote that the society may be a collection of "foolish" individuals, but when those individuals join to form a society their collective judgment becomes "wise" and "always acts right" [Leon,1979:75]. Any proposal for change, regardless of the sound thought that produced it. could not attract the same commitment that an institution could develop over time.

The argument that democracy can be destabilizing dates back to earlier theorists of political order [Huntington, 1968] [Zolberg, 1966], but has been revived by more recent analysts of the developmental state [Leftwich, 1998: 17 -51]. It has also proved popular with many Third World leaders, both the older post independence generation (such as Houphouet Boigny in the Ivory Coast, Nyerere in Tanzania or Sukarno in Indonesia) who argued that only one-party system or 'guided' democracies were needed to contain the social tensions in multiethnic post-colonial states, and a new generation who claim (like Mahathir in Malaysia or Museveni of Uganda) that unrestrained multi-party competition and too much emphasis on political and civil rights tend to destabilize even democracy itself.

On the contrary though, democratic states suffer from conflicts just as others do, and the presence of democracy is no guarantee of a society without prejudice or violence. Democratic societies tend to develop the institutions, resources and flexibility, in the long term. to peacefully manage these kinds of conflict [IDEA, 1998: 13].

As Horowitz (1993: 18-38) argues, there is no case to be made for the futility of democracy or the

inevitability of uncontrolled conflict. Even in the most severely divided society, ties of blood do not lead ineluctably to rivers of blood. Similarly, Bose suggests that to endorse the claim that plural societies are incompatible with democratic values, seems to imply that 'plural societies' the world over are condemned to an undemocratic future simply because of their plural composition. If this is correct, it would appear that democratic aspirations are a futile fantasy for the vast majority of humankind [1995:87-116].

In addition, thereof the national mass media is crucial to the national democratic process. It is the national mass media that holds the key to reaching millions of voters. It is essential therefore that the media is open and transparent, accountable to the public as freedom of press is balanced with its accountability, divers in the sense that media monopolies should not be allowed to develop and dominate. It was with regards to these, that Tunji Olaopa argued that a system of continuing assessment by which a system determines the effectiveness of its career and professional development as well as training effectiveness, need to be put in place. This assessment he said, will help to achieve the continue learning and improvement concern through progressive modification and therefore improvement of the existing system [2008:89).

Summary/Conclusion

It is quite possible to have accountability in the high politics of the state, nest rulers and free elections, and yet profound injustice or irresponsibility in the deep politics of society, that is, the elections between rich and poor, powerful and weak [Lonsdale, 1986: 130). The institutions and mechanisms of representative democracies are the main objects of the analysis of the quality of a democracy in this study. This is not to ignore the direct democracy as the highest expression of democratic quality, but to acknowledge the secular experience of representative democracies and their real potential for improvement. As the analysis is being used on representative democracies, then the accountability - a core feature in the experience of representative democracy - becomes a truly central dimension in so much as it grants citizens and civil society in general an effective means of control over political institutions. This feature attenuates the difficulties that objectively exist when there is a shift from direct to representative democracy.

Accountability is implicitly based on two assumptions from the liberal tradition that highlight the interconnectedness of all of the dimensions explained above. The first assumption is that if citizens are genuinely given the opportunity to evaluate the responsibility of government in terms of its satisfaction of their own needs and requests, they are in fact capable of doing so, possessing above all a relatively accurate perception of their own needs. The second assumption is that, citizens, either alone or as part of a group, are the only possible judges of their own needs, no third party can decide those needs. To leave these assumptions unmentioned is mistaken, they should instead be stated and taken

into account from outset. It is also erroneous to consider each of them as a mere ideological choice. It is instead important to acknowledge that western democracies have followed a liberal-democratic trajectory and that any concrete analysis of the quality of democracy must take this into account and shift towards a direction marked by more egalitarian choices [Larry, 1995].

As a result, this paper concluded that democracy is built and sustained by the participation of a wide range of citizens and interests' groups. Together with other citizens and segments of society, the business sector must play its part in democratic development. As a key component of civil society, business possesses resources, human capital, and problem-solving capabilities that can benefit society as a whole [Peter and Micheal,2000:22). Therefore, there is an ample need to defend and engage the private sectors to improve policymaking, represent legitimate economic interests, defend democratic rights and institutions.

Khosa notes on a project entitled "Closing the gap between policy and implantation in South Africa", that: "... the discrepancies between policy and implementation are largely caused by unrealistic policies, and a lack of managerial expertise [2003:49). Another key finding in this study was that policy implementation suffered from the absence of a people driven process. Culminating into insufficient coordination of policy implementation, which is cited in virtually all sectors, and has significantly hampered, the implementation of policies. In addition, insufficient staffing and capacity of all three spheres of government, as well as the linkages between them, have largely worked against the successful implementation of policies. These findings would have an adverse effect on successful service delivery [Petrus, 2005:8-9][Gill,2003:1].

Finally successful implementation is a matter of degree and clearly, a relative concept. We have to think of it in terms of the extent to which it has occurred rather than whether it has occurred. Success, in the case of implementation, is not a matter of absolutes.

Recommendations

To be the foremost "agents of change" in the war against corruption and other related offences in the polity there is need to restore Nigeria to the enviable status of respectable, dignity and honour within the comity of nations. i) Democratic Institutions in Nigeria should be strengthened while the costs of policy Implementation is acceptable and reasonable; ii) Implementation of policies should take place within a reasonable time frame, that is, if one expected implementation to be completed within five years and it has been fifteen and the job is not yet completed questions should be asked by the people or its representatives; iii) Democratic institutions should be granted autonomy to pursue its aims and objectives; iv) Policies should have the nominally intended effect on the intended target population;

v) Government should provide an atmosphere for fashioning out modalities to the sustainability of democratic values in Nigeria; vi) Need to promote effective institutionalization in Nigerian democratic system; vii) The various elements of fostering policy implementation network should be a catalyst for change in Nigeria's Democracy; viii) Special courts should be provided for the anti-graft agencies (Economic and Financial Crimes Commission - EFCC and Independent Corrupt Practices and Commission - ICPC) to try corrupt offenders across the country this would curb unnecessary delays in prosecuting those who are guilty of graft; ix) Strengthen linkages among key sectors of the economy; x) Government policies should be realigned to encourage consistency and continuity in government action; xi) Promote an efficient, accountable, transparent and participatory government; xii) Government should restore trust and confidence between leaders and citizens; xiii) Promote effective enforcement of the rule of law; xiv) Adequate funding arrangement should be in place for the agencies in view; xv) Most importantly there should be vigorous actions to fight corruption and organized crimes.

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